

Parental Awareness of Child Labor Laws and Welfare Schemes for Female Child Labor: A Study in Kurnool District

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Abstract

Child labor remains a pervasive violation of human rights, drawing global attention to the welfare of children. The 20th century marked a significant turning point in the advancement of child welfare, leading to heightened awareness of children's rights as distinct individuals. This study aims to assess the level of parental awareness regarding government welfare schemes designed to support female child laborers. Our findings reveal that 46.3% of respondents acknowledge that child labor forces children into premature adulthood, leaving them vulnerable to exploitation due to their vulnerability. Furthermore, 33.5% of respondents recognize that a sense of inferiority among child laborers stifles their courage and creativity. The creation of additional employment opportunities for unskilled and unemployed individuals in rural areas can contribute to economic growth. Implementing awareness generation programs focusing on child labor laws and involving various stakeholders such as government departments, youth associations, self-help groups (SHGs), and civil society members is crucial for reducing the prevalence of child labor.

Keywords: Child Labor, Welfare, Female Child Labor, Economic Development, Legislation, Parental Awareness

Introduction

Child labor remains a pressing concern in India, with a pronounced presence in rural areas. Although legislative measures have been introduced worldwide to restrict the employment of children below a certain age and define acceptable conditions for minors working in various professions, the effectiveness of laws designed to protect children from hazardous labor is often lacking. In many instances, children find themselves aiding family members in agricultural endeavors, working as part of contractual family labor arrangements, or participating in plantation work. Rural India witnesses a common practice of school-aged children engaging in agricultural work as part of their family responsibilities. Regrettably, the implementation of Child Labor Laws at the state and district levels has been inadequate.

This study seeks to shed light on the perspectives of parents and employers regarding child labor issues, aiming to enhance their awareness, knowledge, and understanding of the prevalence and conditions of child labor within the study area. The situation of female child laborers is especially distressing due to gender discrimination prevalent in many Indian societies. Agriculture, which contributes three-fourths of the national income and supports over 75 percent of the population for subsistence, is heavily intertwined with child labor. Poverty and the absence of social security remain primary drivers of child labor, trapping children in work that offers limited opportunities for physical, social, and mental development. Both girls and boys are ensnared in the worst forms of child labor, but societal expectations, duties, and responsibilities imposed on girls often render them more susceptible to exploitation. Addressing the issue of female child labor is a complex challenge, compounded by the fact that the labor of female children is often unacknowledged or underrepresented in formal labor statistics. The absence of quality universal education further contributes to children dropping out of school and entering the labor force, making it difficult to accurately detect the true extent of child labor.

Welfare schemes for female child labor are essential in combating this pervasive violation of human rights. Child welfare has garnered global attention,

particularly in the 20th century, with growing awareness of children's rights as independent entities. Article 18 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child in 1989 emphasizes the need to protect children from economic exploitation and hazardous work that interferes with their education, health, or overall development. The International Labor Organization (ILO) also opposes child labor, particularly in situations where children face educational and social disadvantages or work in exploitative conditions harmful to their well-being.

The Indian Government recognizes child labor because of poverty and has taken steps to address it through legislative measures. In 1986, the

Child Labor (Prohibition and Regulation) Act was enacted, replacing the Employment of Children Act of 1938. While the 1986 Act does not completely ban child labor, it focuses on "projecting" working children. The government has established unique schools to rehabilitate children engaged in dangerous or hazardous occupations, offering them education, vocational training, monthly stipends, and nutrition and health services.

The commitment of the Government of India to eradicate child labor is enshrined in the Constitution, which provides for the protection of children from engaging in economic activities unsuitable for their age. The Directive Principles of State Policy in the Constitution reinforce this commitment. The Central Labor Service (CLS), established in 1987, aims to improve industrial relations, labor welfare, and the enforcement of labor laws. Various schemes offering medical, housing, educational, recreational, water supply, and family welfare benefits are implemented for workers as part of the government's ongoing efforts to safeguard the welfare of children and laborers.

Material and Methodology

Objectives

The present study broadly aims at studying the socio-economic and social participation, employment support and knowledge on welfare schemes available to female child labors. The following are the main objectives of the present study:

- To study the level of knowledge on welfare schemes provided by the Government for girl child labor.
- To study the level of knowledge on girl child rights
- To examine the economic and social conditions of female child labor in the sample district.

Sample design and study area

The researcher has purposively selected the Kurnool district due to its proximity and familiarity. Stratified random sampling method was used in selection of study sample. The study has conducted in six Mandal's of three revenue divisions of the Kurnool district. Four villages from each Mandal were selected. 20 respondents each were selected at random in 24 villages and the total sample is comprises of 480 female child labor residing in agricultural families in the Kurnool district for the present study.

Results

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the respondents

A study of the background characteristics of sampled population is an important task in the study. Several studies have been shown that there is a strong relationship between socio-economic status and Girl Child Labor in Agriculture Families.

Table No.1: Percentage Distribution of the respondents by their Socio-Demographic Characteristics (N=480)

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the respondents	Frequency	Percent
Age of the Respondent		
5-8 Year	47	9.8
9-11 Years	115	24.0
12-14 Years	318	66.2
Religion		
Hindu	242	50.4
Muslim	59	12.3
Christian	146	30.4

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Others	33	6.9
Education		
pre-school	137	28.5
Primary	98	20.4
Upper-Primary	177	36.9
High School	68	14.2
Work Experience (Years)		
≤ 2 Years	151	31.5
2- 4Years	223	46.5
≥ 4 Years	106	22.1
Girl Child Income		
≤ 5000	16	3.3
5001 and above	464	96.7
Source of Family Income		
Agriculture	177	36.9
Allied Labor	155	32.3
Business	45	9.4
Others	103	21.5

Age plays an important role in measuring the respondent's perception on their present working condition. Data has been collected on the girls who involved in the agriculture labor to analyze the girl's working condition in the agriculture field. In the study area nearly two-thirds (66.3 %) of the respondents were in 12-14 years age group. One-fourth (24.0 %) of them were in 9-11 years and the remaining (9.8 %) were in the age group of 5-9 years. One half (50.4 %) of the respondents were Hindus, less than one-third (30.4 %) of them were Christians, 12.3 percent were Muslims and 6.9 percent belong to other religions. It is observed from the above table that more than one third (36.9 %) of the respondents have completed upper-primary education in the study area. More than one-fourth (28.5%) the girls had pre-school education and two-fifth (20.4 %) had primary education and 14.2 percent of the respondents had high school education. More than two-fourth (46.5 %) of the respondents were having ≤ 2 years of experience in the agriculture field, less than one-third (31.5 %) of them were working experience of 2-4 years and more than one-fifth (22.1 %) of them were working 4 years and above in the agriculture field. Almost all (96.7 %) of the respondents were getting a monthly income Rs. 5000 and above the study area. More than one-third (36.9 %) of the respondents' parents were having agriculture background, followed by allied labor (32.3%) and other types of activities (21.5 %).

The data was collected on parents opinion on child labor, sociological and economical aspects of the girl child labors in agricultural families namely on 1) fulfillment of social obligation 2) prone to habits like smoking, gambling and extravagancy 3) loss of potential intellectuals and thinkers in 4) prone to exploitation 5) violation of human rights 6) enforcement of laws 7) punishment under child labor laws 8) parents knowledge on girl child welfare schemes etc.

Table No. 3: Percentage distribution of the respondents by Parents opinion on Sociological and economical aspects of female child labor

Sociological aspects		Agree	Disagree	Un- Decided	Total
GCs need proper nurture and nourishment to make them best fits in future life	N	355	71	54	480
	P	74	14.8	11.3	100
CL has no rationale as it is the decision of the parent who are second to none as well wishes of children	N	256	160	64	480
	P	53.3	33.3	13.3	100
CL is not unethical rather fulfillment of social obligation by employers towards poor of whom government fails to take care of	N	199	173	108	480
	P	41.5	36	22.5	100
CL keeps children away from education and breeds illiteracy in a society	N	209	187	84	480
	P	43.5	39	17.5	100
Working children are prone to the habits of smoking, gambling, and extravagancy	N	209	200	71	480
	P	43.5	41.7	14.8	100
Child labor compels children to lead pre-mature adults' lives	N	222	161	97	480
	P	46.3	33.5	20.2	100
	N	225	188	67	480

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CL has high opportunity cost as it leads to loss of potential intellectuals and thinkers	P	46.9	39.2	14	100
Inferiority complex suppresses courage and creativity of children	N	161	95	224	480
	P	33.5	19.8	46.7	100
Children as workers are prone to exploitation by reason of their docility	N	164	157	159	480
	P	34.2	32.7	33.1	100
Child labor is an off school of poverty which is the result of unequal distribution of wealth	N	288	141	51	480
	P	60	29.4	106	100

In the table no.3 shows that 33.5 percent of the respondents agreed that inferiority complex among the children will suppress their courage and creativity. 46.3% of the respondents agreed that child labor compels children to lead premature adults and there is a chance to exploit by reason of their docility. 43.5 percent of the respondents agreed that child labor leads to children keep away from education and breeds illiteracy in society. 46.9 percent of the respondents agreed that child labor is one of the opportunities to forego the potential intellectuals and thinkers of nation. Nearly three-fifth (60 %) of the respondent's parents opinioned that unequal distribution of wealth is one of the reasons for child labor as it leads to more dropouts. Nearly three-fourth (74 %) of the parents agreed that girl child require proper nurture and nourishment to make them best fits in future life.

Table No 4: Percentage distribution of the respondents by Parents opinion on Sociological and economical aspects of female child labor

Knowledge on Legal aspects		Agree	Disagree	Un-Decided	Total
Employing CL is a violation of human rights	N	235	211	34	480
	P	49	44	7.1	100
Employment of children in hazardous work is a crime	N	201	200	79	480
	P	41.9	41.7	16.5	100

Child labor is a moral crime against humanity	N	217	183	80	480
	P	45.2	38.1	16.7	100
Hazardous nature of job coupled with excessive workload and long hours of work are so heinous crime	N	138	226	116	480
	P	28.8	47.1	24.2	100
Child labor is a punishment to tender hands for no fault of theirs	N	111	267	102	480
	P	23.1	55.6	21.3	100
CL laws fail as these are unacceptable to people with unsound financial position	N	148	251	81	480
	P	30.8	52.3	16.9	100
Weak enforcement of laws leads to child labor with impunity	N	141	209	130	480
	P	29.4	43.5	27.1	100
The parents of child workers shall be booked under the relevant laws	N	144	166	170	480
	P	30	34.6	35.4	100
Child labor shall be completely banned in all aspects	N	202	205	73	480
	P	42.1	42.7	15.2	100
The employers of CL shall be dealt with stringent punitive measures	N	136	243	101	480
	P	28.3	50.6	21	100
Enforcement of child labor laws shall be strictly observed	N	155	275	50	480
	P	32.3	57.3	10.4	100
Child labor is subject to punishment under child labor laws.	N	167	112	201	480
	P	34.8	23.3	41.9	100

In this study an attempt is made to assess the parents' opinion on the sociological and economical aspect of the child labors related aspects. Nearly one-half (49 %) of the respondent's agreed that working as a child labor is violation of human rights. 45.2 percent of respondents accepted that child labor is moral crime against humanity and 41.9 percent of the respondents agreed that employment of child in hazardous work is

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crime and 28.8 percent of respondent's expressed that excessive workload and long hours of work in hazardous Work is heinous crime. Only one-third (29.4 %) of the parents were having knowledge on child labor laws as they expressed that the Child labor laws are failed in implementation and weak enforcement of law were the causes of child labor. Nearly one-third (32.3 %) of parents expressed that they have observed strict enforcement of child labor laws. 30% of the respondents were agreed that parents of the child labor should be punished under the child labor laws. More than one-third (34.8 %) of the respondents were aware that child labor is subject punishment under child labor laws. 42.1 percent of the respondents agreed that child labor shall be banned in all aspects. It is interesting to note that more than two-fifth (41.5 %) of the parents agreed that child labor is not an unethical and the employers of the child labor were giving an opportunity to get the financial source for those who are neglected by the governments.

The findings from the above table shows that majority of the parents were aware of the ill effects of the child labor and the laws and functioning of law enforcement authorities related to child labor.

Parent's knowledge on various welfare schemes implemented by the government to avoid Child Labor is presented in the table no. 5. Cent percent of the respondents (100 %) in the study area agreed that free education for girls up to higher education will help to eradicate the child labor. Higher proportion (85 %) of the respondent's expressed that Balika Sam Rakshana scheme is very useful to balance sex ratio and prevent gender discrimination and the scheme is also encouraging employment skills, opportunities and creates awareness on health and family life education to girl Child. More than one-half (51.7 %) of the respondents felt that Apana Beti Apne desh scheme is providing rehabilitation services for those who were rescued from child labor and brothel home. Similar percentage (62.5 %) of the respondents agreed that strict implementation of prenatal diagnostic technique act helps in reducing female feticides and the gender discrimination. The girl child agreed that implementing the constitutional provisions and human rights for girl child reduces gender discrimination (60 %) and welfare measures are sufficient to improve the girl child status provided by the government and non-government organizations (60.2 %). More than one-half (52.5 %) of the respondents agreed that national policy for children and legal enactment facilitates the development of girl child.

Table No. 5: Percentage distribution of the respondents by Parents knowledge on welfare schemes for female child labor

Parents knowledge on welfare schemes	Agree	Disagree	Total

Free education for girls up to degree level is very beneficial for girl education	N	480	0	480
	P	100	0.0	100.0
Balika samrakshna pathakam is very useful to balance sex ratio and prevent gender discrimination	N	408	72	480
	P	85	15	100
The KB scheme is encouraging employment skills, opportunities, and health awareness of girl children	N	290	190	480
	P	60.4	39.6	100
KB scheme is providing awareness on family life education to girl children	N	290	190	480
	P	60.4	39.6	100.0
ABAD programmer is very useful to rehabilitate the girls who are rescued from CL and brothel home	N	248	232	480
	P	51.7	48.3	100.0
Strict implementation of pre -natal diagnostic technique Act, 1994 helps in reducing female feticides	N	300	180	480
	P	62.5	37.5	100.0
Constitutional provision and human rights for GC reduces gender discrimination	N	288	192	480
	P	60	40	100.0
National policy for children and legal enactments facilitates development of GC	N	252	228	480
	P	52.5	47.5	100.0
The present welfare measures taken by govt; NGOs are sufficient to improve the girl child status	N	289	191	480
	P	60.2	39.8	100.0

Conclusion

Equality of opportunities is the foundation of modern welfare states. The crucial role that education can play in the reduction of girl child labor and improvement in the economic wellbeing of individuals can go a long way in achieving such ends. In India, poverty remains the key determinant of children not being sent to school. Most of the parents are not able to afford to send them to school. The path to progress in terms reducing the number of girl child laborer's by taking into consideration the cultural and economic measures, their future will continue to remain bleak. The study suggests that promotions of non-agricultural economic activities like micro and small industries and

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self-employment with the support of SHG groups (Women Groups) are the best alternatives to improve employment and income generation for the rural poor. Creation of more employment opportunities to the unskilled Unemployed will help to economic growth in rural areas. Through awareness generation programmes related to the Child Labor Laws with involvement of convergent departments, youth associations, SHGs, Civil Society members will be helping to decrease the number of child labors. Educate the parents of girl child on importance of sufficient nutritious food and proper education for the growth of girl child and its impact on future generations.

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